

TABLE 1—POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION DATA OF THE OXIDATION OF HYDRAZINE BY Mn^{3+}

Cell: 10 ml M/40 Hydrazine sulphate, Medium: 9N H_2SO_4 ; Oxidant: M/10 Mn^{3+} solution.

Storage time for attaining equilibrium at room temperature	Position of inflexion in ml	Nature of inflexion
1 hr.	2.5	very sharp sharp
	5.1	
12 hrs.	2.5	sharp sharp sharp sharp
	5.1	
	7.5	
	10.3	
Solution heated for 2 hrs. at 90° and cooled		
24 hrs.	5.1	medium sharp medium sharp sharp
	7.5	
	10.4	

Results and Discussions

Four sharp inflexions at 2.5, 5.1, 7.5 and 10.3 ml of oxidant were observed at room temperature as expected, 10 ml of M/40 hydrazine solution on reacting with 2.5 ml of M/10 Mn^{3+} solution gave a colourless species which initiated vinyl polymerisation. This may be N_2H_3 (hydrazyl) radical¹. Since, the solution is colourless, it is expected that no species of manganese of higher oxidation state than Mn^{3+} is present and thus only species present in solution capable of initiating polymerisation may be the oxidised form of hydrazine.

In the oxidation of hydrazine¹⁰ by copper(II), in spite of the low redox potentials of copper(II)-copper(I) couple, aquo copper(II) is found to oxidise N_2H_3 to N_2H_2 . Formation of N_2H_3 is cited in many cases and supported in literature^{11,12}.

The mixture, 10 ml of M/40 hydrazine solution and 5 ml of M/10 Mn^{3+} solution, probably gave a species diimide (N_2H_2), which was inferred from the reduction of fumaric acid by the above species to succinic acid⁵.

The observed stoichiometry of the overall reaction can be given as

The complete deelectronation of hydrazine can be represented by the following one electron step equations:

On heating the solution for two hours at 90° and storage for 24 hours, the first inflexion (i) vanished which may be due to the short life of the hydrazyl radical. All the other inflexions are found to be

less sharp, but the position does not change to any significant extent.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (L. N. C.) acknowledges thankfulness to Ranchi University for providing him financial support for the research work and also to Prof. G. Mishra and C. M. Singh for fruitful discussions.

References

- H. C. MISHRA and R. N. P. SINHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1300.
- R. K. PRASAD and A. KUMAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 819.
- H. E. KIRK and A. W. BROWNE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 337.
- A. KUMAR and R. K. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 366.
- T. HUANG and J. T. SPENCE, *J. Phys. Chem. Ithaca*, 1968, 72, 4198.
- A. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic analysis', Longmans, Third edition, 1961, 327.
- G. DAVIS and K. KUSTIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 484.
- G. DAVIS and K. KUSTIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 2248.
- A. R. J. P. UBBELOHDE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1505.
- B. P. GYANI and S. N. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 32, 313.
- J. W. CAHN and R. E. POWELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2568.
- J. Q. ADAMS and J. R. THOMAS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 39, 1904.
- H. R. FALLE, *Canad. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 46, 1703.

Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II), UO_2^{2+} and VO^{2+} complexes of *o*-(2-pyrrolideneimino)benzoic acid and 3-(2-pyrrolideneimino)propionic acid

N. K. SANKHLA, P. K. KANUNGO and R. K. MEHTA
Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur
Manuscript received 14 April 1978, revised 29 August 1978,
accepted 8 September 1978

O-(2-PYRROLIDENEIMINO)BENZOIC acid (H_2PB) and 3-(2-pyrrolideneimino)propionic acid (H_2PP) derived from pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and anthranilic acid or β -alanine are structurally similar and are expected to behave as biprotic tridentates. They for solid complexes with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II), UO_2^{2+} and VO^{2+} .

Chemicals and apparatus used in the investigations are the same as reported earlier¹.

Preparation of H_2PB and H_2PP (Pfeiffer's Method²):

A mixture of alcoholic solution of pyrrole-2-

carboxaldehyde (0.95 g) and anthranilic acid (1.317 g) or β -alanine (0.89 g) was refluxed for half an hour. The solution was filtered hot, concentrated and cooled to give tobacco-coloured crystals of H_2PB or dark red crystal of H_2PP . m.p. 180° (H_2PB). 120° (H_2PP).

Metal Complexes: These were prepared by refluxing a mixture of the metal acetate (0.005 mole in 10-15 ml 80% ethanol) and H_2PB or H_2PP (0.005 mole in 30-50 ml 80% ethanol) on a steam-bath for 2-4 hours. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised. The pyridine adducts of these complexes were obtained by the method reported earlier⁸.

Based on elemental analysis and molecular weight data the metal complexes and their pyridine adducts display 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry and may possess the composition $[MLX_n]$, where M = metal-ion, X = H_2O or pyridine and $LH_2 = [C_{12}H_{10}N_2O_2]$ or $[C_8H_{10}N_2O_2]$. Thermogravimetric analyses of these complexes show a weight loss compared to three water molecules ($n=3$) when M = Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II), two water molecules ($n=2$) when M = VO^{2+} and one water molecule ($n=1$) when M = Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II) or UO_2^{2+} .

The magnetic moments indicate the presence of 4, 3, 2, 1 and 1 unpaired electrons in Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and VO^{2+} complexes and their pyridine adducts respectively and the remaining complexes were found to be diamagnetic. From these values it is apparent that spin-spin interaction does not occur in these complexes and they exist as monomers. The electronic spectra of the complexes supported by the magnetic data suggest nearly octahedral structure for the Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and VO^{2+} complexes and a square-planar stereochemistry for the Pd(II) complexes. Negligibly small ($4.9-9.2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) conductance values of the compounds suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

The I.R. spectra of H_2PB and H_2PP consist of bands in the regions $3320-3180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $2570-2560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1695-1680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1660-1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu N-H$, $\nu COOH$, $\nu C=O$ and $\nu C=N$, respectively. In the metal complexes the bands in the region $2570-2560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappeared suggesting coordination through the carboxylate group. $\nu C=N$ of H_2PB and H_2PP was shifted to lower frequency side due to complexation. The appearance of two new bands in the regions $670-640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $600-580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes suggest M-O and M-N bonds formation. All the complexes indicate one broad band at around 3400 cm^{-1} due to νOH of water molecule present.

Thus it is apparent that the general similarity in the complexes of the two ligands is due to the presence of the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group in β -position to the carboxylic group. This

result is also in agreement with the findings of Kubo⁴.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to UGC (India) for the award of a fellowship to one of them (NKS).

References

1. R. K. GUPTA and R. K. MEHTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **11**, 56.
2. P. PFEIFFER, W. OFFERMANN and H. WERNER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1942, **159**, 313.
3. R. K. MEHTA, S. P. RAO and R. C. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 933.
4. M. KUBO, Y. KURODA, M. KISHITA and Y. MUTO, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1963, **16**, 7.

Potentiometric Studies on Ternary Complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II)

KIRAN KAPOOR and G. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra

Manuscript received 26 April 1978, revised 7 August 1978, accepted 31 August 1978

THE binary complexes of some bivalent metals such as Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} or Pb^{2+} with picolinic and quinaldonic acids¹ have been studied and the stability constants of metal picolinates reported². Martell et al^{3,4} carried out studies on the ternary complexes of Cu^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} with 8-HQS as one of the ligands and heterocyclic base or aminopolycarboxylic acid as the other ligand. The review of the literature, however, reveals that no investigations on the ternary system of Zn(II) and Cd(II) involving oxine-5-sulphonic acid have been carried out. In the present communication the results on the potentiometric studies of the ternary systems: Zn(II)/Cd(II)-8.HQS-HA (where 8-HQS = 8-hydroxyquinoline, 5-sulphonic acid; HA = quinaldonic acid (QUINA) or picolinic acid (PIC)) have been discussed.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR BDH grade. Stock solutions of metal nitrates were prepared and standardized by their usual methods (Zinc as $ZnNH_4PO_4$ and cadmium as $Cd(C_7H_6O_2N)_2$). The ligand solutions were prepared by direct weighing. All the titrations were carried out in duplicate at temperature $35 \pm 1^\circ$ keeping total volume (50 ml), concentration ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$ in metal or ligand) and ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) constant at the beginning of the titration. pH measurements were made with Philips precision pH meter (PR 9405M) using standard glass and calomel electrodes.

Results and Discussion

A sharp inflection at $m=1$ in the case of 8-HQS